

España (ES)

Environmental sensitivity to wind farms

Wind power capacity factor (CF) at 100 m. height

Wind power capacity at ISA-4 and $CF \geq 0.285$

Wind power potential vs. capacity factor

- **LAND: 9.16%** of the region combines low environmental sensitivity (ISA-4) and high wind resource ($CF > 0.285$).
- **WIND POWER CAPACITY: 456.49 GW** could be installed in these areas.
Installed wind power capacity in España in 2025 was **32.60 GW**.
- **ENERGY: 1389.01 TWh** could be generated with this potential capacity.
This represents around **563%** of the actual electricity demand in the region (246.65 TWh).